

Original article

Prevalence and determinants of occupational hazard exposure among timber processing workers in Kano state, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Occupational hazard exposure remains a major public health concern among workers in informal-sector industries such as timber processing, where exposure to wood dust, noise, and mechanical hazards is common. Evidence on its magnitude and determinants in northern Nigeria is limited. This study assessed the prevalence and determinants of occupational hazard exposure among timber processing workers in Kano State, Nigeria. **Materials and Methods:** A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 406 timber processing workers in Tarauni Local Government Area between March and May 2025. Participants were selected using a multistage sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire and an observation checklist. Descriptive statistics summarised hazard prevalence, while chi-square and multivariable logistic regression analyses identified factors associated with occupational hazard exposure at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** Occupational hazard exposure was high, with wood dust (90.1%), loud noise (86.7%), and unguarded machinery (78.1%) being the most common hazards. Continuous exposure to wood dust and noise was reported by 71.2% and 59.9% of workers, respectively. Workplace safety infrastructure was inadequate, with only 30.0% reporting a functional first aid kit and 16.5% having undergone occupational health screening. Workers with formal education (aOR = 2.41; 95% CI: 1.10–5.29), those employed in structured settings (aOR = 4.15; 95% CI: 2.08–8.28), and those with more than five years of experience (aOR = 2.18; 95% CI: 1.19–3.97) had significantly lower hazard exposure. **Conclusion:** Occupational hazard exposure among timber workers is high and influenced by workplace and socioeconomic factors. Strengthening occupational safety systems and health education is essential.

Keywords: Informal sector, Nigeria, Occupational hazard exposure, Timber workers.

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ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20669744>

Date Submitted: 20th March 2026

Date Accepted: 2nd May 2026

Date Published Online: 12th June 2026

Cite this article as Muhammad A. Sani, Umar Shuaibu, Ibrahim S. Aliyu, Adamu Alhaji, Muhammad A. Baba, Mamuda A. Sabo, Abubakar Ibrahim, Umar Bello, Hassan F. Hassan, Hassan Y. Ahmad, Aisha S. Saad. Prevalence and Determinants of Occupational Hazard Exposure among Timber Processing Workers in Kano State, Nigeria. *The Scholar J Health Sci* 2026; 2(1): 281-289.

Introduction

Occupational hazards remain a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where occupational health systems are often underdeveloped. The International Labour Organisation estimates that millions of workers are exposed annually to hazardous conditions that contribute to occupational injuries and diseases.¹ Globally, work-related accidents and illnesses result in substantial economic losses, reduced productivity, and long-term disability.² Exposure to workplace hazards such as dust, noise, chemical fumes, mechanical risks, and poor ergonomic conditions is a key determinant of occupational health outcomes.³

Prolonged exposure to wood dust has been associated with respiratory conditions, including chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, asthma, allergic reactions, and certain malignancies.^{4 5} Similarly, sustained exposure to high levels of industrial noise contributes to irreversible noise-induced hearing loss, one of the most prevalent occupational health problems globally.^{6 7} The timber processing industry represents a high-risk occupational sector, particularly within the informal economy. Workers in sawmills and carpentry workshops are frequently exposed to wood dust, excessive machine-generated noise, unguarded machinery, poor ventilation, and unsafe work practices.^{8 9} These conditions significantly increase the risk of both acute injuries, such as lacerations and fractures, and chronic health effects associated with prolonged exposure.^{10 11} In sub-Saharan Africa, occupational hazard exposure is exacerbated by weak enforcement of occupational safety regulations, inadequate engineering controls, and limited access to personal protective equipment.^{12 13} Studies conducted in countries such as Ghana and Ethiopia have reported high prevalence of wood dust and noise exposure among timber workers, largely due to poor workplace safety systems.^{14 15} Similar patterns have been observed in other African settings where informal sector workers operate in poorly regulated environments.^{16 17} In Nigeria, the informal sector accounts for a significant share of employment, including timber processing. Despite the existence of national occupational safety policies, implementation remains weak, particularly in informal industries where regulatory enforcement and workplace inspections are limited.^{18 19} Previous studies among Nigerian sawmill workers have documented high exposure to wood dust and mechanical hazards, with inadequate hazard control measures.^{20 21}

However, there is limited evidence on the magnitude of occupational hazard exposure and its associated factors among timber processing workers in Northern Nigeria. Tarauni Local Government Area of Kano State hosts numerous timber processing workshops operating largely under informal conditions. Workers in this setting are frequently exposed to occupational hazards, with minimal access to structured safety measures and occupational health services. Understanding the prevalence and determinants of occupational hazard exposure in this context is essential for designing targeted interventions to improve worker safety. Therefore, this study aimed to assess the prevalence and determinants of occupational hazard exposure among timber processing workers in Kano State, Nigeria. **The specific objectives were to:** Determine the prevalence of occupational hazard exposure among timber processing workers. Identify socio-demographic factors associated with occupational hazard exposure. Assess workplace-related factors associated with occupational hazard exposure.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional design to assess the prevalence and determinants of occupational hazard exposure among timber processing workers. The cross-sectional approach allows for simultaneous assessment of exposure and associated factors within a defined population at a single point in time and is widely used in occupational health and epidemiological research.²²

Study Area

The study was conducted in Tarauni Local Government Area (LGA) of Kano State, Nigeria. Kano State is located in the northwestern region of Nigeria and is one of the most industrially active states in the country. Tarauni LGA hosts numerous timber processing workshops and sawmills operating largely within the informal sector. These facilities are characterised by manual and semi-mechanised wood processing activities, limited engineering controls, inadequate ventilation, and

weak enforcement of occupational safety standards, thereby exposing workers to hazards such as wood dust, excessive noise, mechanical injuries, and chemical fumes.^{23 24}

Study Period

The study was conducted between March and May 2025.

Study Population

The study population comprised timber processing workers operating within registered and unregistered timber workshops and sawmills in Tarauni LGA. This included workers engaged in sawing, machine operation, carpentry, finishing and polishing, loading and material handling, as well as apprentices involved in timber processing activities.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Workers aged 18 years and above who had been engaged in timber processing activities for at least six months and provided informed consent were included in the study. Workers who were severely ill, absent during data collection, or declined participation were excluded.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size was determined using the single population proportion formula:

$$n = Z^2P(1 - P) / d^2$$

Where:

Z = 1.96 at 95% confidence level

P = 48% (based on a previous study in Nigeria)

d = 0.05 margin of error

The minimum sample size calculated was 384. After adjusting for a 10% non-response rate, the final sample size was 422. However, a total of 406 respondents participated in the study.

Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was employed. First, five timber processing clusters were identified within Tarauni LGA. Second, three clusters were selected using simple random sampling.

The required sample size was proportionally allocated to each selected cluster based on the estimated number of workers in each cluster. Within each cluster, systematic sampling was applied using a sampling interval (k) calculated by dividing the total number of workers by the required sample size. Eligible workers were then selected consecutively until the required sample size was achieved.

Data Collection Instruments

Data were collected using a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire and a workplace observation checklist developed based on established occupational health and safety guidelines.²⁵ The questionnaire captured information on sociodemographic characteristics, occupational history, hazard exposure, workplace safety infrastructure, and occupational health practices.

The observation checklist was used to validate workplace environmental conditions and assess the availability of hazard control measures.²⁶

Validity and Reliability of Instrument

The questionnaire was adapted from previously validated occupational health survey tools and reviewed by experts in public health and occupational safety to ensure content validity. A pretest was conducted among 10% of the sample size in a similar setting outside the study area, and necessary modifications were made.

Reliability of the instrument was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which yielded a value of 0.82, indicating good internal consistency.

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected by trained research assistants experienced in occupational health surveys. Participants were approached at their workplaces, informed about the study objectives, and written informed consent was obtained. Interviews were conducted in a private setting within the workplace to ensure confidentiality.

Workplace environmental observations were conducted concurrently using the observation checklist to enhance the validity of exposure assessment.²⁷

Study Variables

Dependent Variable

The dependent variable was occupational hazard exposure, defined as self-reported exposure to at least one workplace hazard (wood dust, noise, mechanical hazards, or chemical fumes) during routine work activities.

Respondents were categorized as:

Exposed (1): if they reported at least one hazard

Not exposed (0): if no exposure was reported

Independent Variables

Independent variables included age, educational level, job category, employment type, years of work experience, and workplace safety infrastructure.

Data Management and Analysis

Completed questionnaires were checked for completeness and consistency prior to data entry.

Data were entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize hazard prevalence using frequencies and percentages. Bivariate analysis using chi-square tests assessed associations between independent variables and occupational hazard exposure.

Variables with p-values less than 0.05 were included in multivariable logistic regression models to identify independent predictors of occupational hazard exposure. Adjusted odds ratios (AOR) with 95% confidence intervals were reported, and statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.²⁸

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Kano State Ministry of Health Research Ethics Committee (Approval No: SHREC/2025/6652) prior to commencement of the study. Permission was also obtained from workshop owners and relevant authorities.

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before participation. Confidentiality of participant information was strictly maintained, and the study adhered to established ethical principles for research involving human subjects.

Results

A total of 406 questionnaires were administered and completed, yielding a response rate of 100.0%.

Sociodemographic Characteristics of Respondents

The mean age of respondents was 34.4 ± 6.8 years. The largest proportion of workers were aged 25–34 years (43.8%), followed by those aged 35–44 years (25.6%), while 7.9% were aged above 44 years.

The majority of respondents were male (89.9%), and 59.4% were married.

Regarding educational level, 26.6% had Qur’anic/Islamic education, 23.6% had primary education, and 18.5% had no formal education, while 14.3% had tertiary education.

In terms of employment type, 43.6% were self-employed, 39.7% were employed, and 16.7% were apprentices.

With respect to work experience, 34.7% had 6–10 years of experience, 27.6% had 1–5 years, while 7.9% had less than one year of experience.

Detailed distribution of sociodemographic characteristics is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of Timber Processing Workers (n = 406)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
19–24	92	22.7
25–34	178	43.8
35–44	104	25.6
>44	32	7.9
Mean \pm SD		34.4 ± 6.8
Gender		
Male	365	89.9
Female	41	10.1
Marital Status		
Single	96	23.6
Married	241	59.4
Divorced	42	10.3
Widowed	19	4.7
Separated	8	2.0
Educational Level		
No formal education	75	18.5
Qur’anic/Islamic	108	26.6
Primary	96	23.6
Secondary	69	17.0
Tertiary	58	14.3
Employment Type		
Self-employed	177	43.6
Employed	161	39.7
Apprentice	68	16.7
Years of Experience		
<1 year	32	7.9
1–5 years	112	27.6
6–10 years	141	34.7
11–15 years	78	19.2
>15 years	43	10.6

Prevalence of Occupational Hazard Exposure

A high prevalence of occupational hazard exposure was observed among timber workers. The most commonly reported hazards were wood dust (90.1%), loud noise (86.7%), and unguarded machinery (78.1%).

Other reported hazards included poor ventilation (73.4%), absence of first aid facilities (70.7%), chemical fumes (55.2%), poor lighting (46.1%), and slippery floor conditions (39.9%).

The detailed distribution of occupational hazard exposure is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Prevalence of Occupational Hazard Exposure among Timber Workers (n = 406)

Occupational Hazard	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Wood dust	366	90.1
Loud noise	352	86.7
Unguarded machinery	317	78.1
Poor ventilation	298	73.4
Absence of first aid box	287	70.7
Chemical fumes	224	55.2
Poor lighting	187	46.1
Slippery floor	162	39.9
Other hazards	49	12.1

Intensity of Hazard Exposure and Workplace Safety Conditions

A large proportion of workers reported frequent exposure to hazards. Exposure to wood dust was reported as “always” by 71.2% of respondents and “often” by 18.0%. Similarly, exposure to loud noise was reported as “always” by 59.9% and “often” by 23.6% of respondents.

Workplace safety infrastructure was generally inadequate. Only 30.0% of respondents reported the availability of a functional first aid kit, 22.9% reported the presence of safety posters or rules, and 16.5% had ever undergone occupational medical check-up.

Further details are presented in Table 3.

Factors Associated with Occupational Hazard Exposure (Bivariate Analysis)

Bivariate analysis showed statistically significant associations between selected variables and occupational hazard exposure.

Workers with formal education were significantly more likely to have lower exposure to occupational hazards (p = 0.027) compared to those with non-formal education.

Employment type was also significantly associated with hazard exposure, with employed workers

having lower exposure compared to self-employed workers (p < 0.001).

Table 3: Intensity of Occupational Hazard Exposure and Workplace Safety Conditions (n = 406)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Exposure to Wood Dust		
Always	289	71.2
Often	73	18.0
Sometimes	29	7.1
Rarely	9	2.2
Never	6	1.5
Exposure to Loud Noise		
Always	243	59.9
Often	96	23.6
Sometimes	42	10.3
Rarely	18	4.4
Never	7	1.7
Workplace Safety Indicators		
Functional first aid kit present	122	30.0
Safety posters/rules available	93	22.9
Ever had occupational medical check-up	67	16.5

Similarly, workers with more than five years of work experience were significantly less likely to be exposed to occupational hazards compared to those with fewer years of experience (p = 0.011).

Detailed results of the bivariate analysis are presented in Table 4.

Predictors of Occupational Hazard Exposure (Multivariate Logistic Regression)

Multivariate logistic regression analysis identified independent predictors of occupational hazard exposure.

Workers with formal education were more likely to have reduced exposure to occupational hazards (aOR = 2.41; 95% CI: 1.10–5.29; p = 0.027) compared to those without formal education.

Similarly, workers who were employed in structured workshop settings were significantly more likely to have lower hazard exposure (aOR =

4.15; 95% CI: 2.08–8.28; $p < 0.001$) compared to self-employed workers.

Workers with more than five years of work experience were also more likely to have reduced hazard exposure (aOR = 2.18; 95% CI: 1.19–3.97; $p = 0.011$).

Table 4: Factors Associated with Occupational Hazard Exposure (Bivariate Analysis) (n = 406)

Variable	Lower Exposure n (%)	Higher Exposure n (%)	χ^2	P-value
Educational Level				
Formal	181 (44.6)	97 (23.9)	4.891	0.027
Non-formal	61 (15.0)	67 (16.5)		
Employment Type				
Employed	172 (42.4)	34 (8.4)	12.417	<0.001
Self-employed	70 (17.2)	130 (32.0)		
Years of Experience				
>5 years	160 (39.4)	76 (18.7)	6.412	0.011
≤5 years	82 (20.2)	88 (21.7)		

χ^2 = Chi-square test; statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Full details of the multivariate analysis are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Predictors of Occupational Hazard Exposure (Multivariate Logistic Regression)

Variable	Adjusted Odds Ratio (aOR)	95% CI	p-value
Formal education	2.41	1.10–5.29	0.027
Employed (vs self-employed)	4.15	2.08–8.28	<0.001
Experience >5 years	2.18	1.19–3.97	0.011

aOR = Adjusted Odds Ratio; CI = Confidence Interval; statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Discussion

This study assessed the prevalence and determinants of occupational hazard exposure among timber processing workers in Kano State, Nigeria. The findings revealed a very high

prevalence of occupational hazard exposure, particularly to wood dust, excessive noise, and mechanical hazards, alongside inadequate workplace safety infrastructure. These findings highlight persistent occupational health risks within informal timber processing environments and underscore the influence of socioeconomic and workplace factors on hazard exposure.

The high level of exposure to wood dust and noise observed in this study reflects the nature of timber processing activities, which involve continuous cutting, sanding, and machine operation, often in poorly ventilated environments. The absence of engineering controls such as dust extraction systems, machine guards, and noise reduction mechanisms likely contributes to the elevated exposure levels. Similar findings have been reported among sawmill workers in Nigeria, where exposure to dust and noise frequently exceeds recommended occupational limits.^{29 30} These results reinforce the substantial occupational health burden faced by workers in informal sector industries.

Comparable patterns have been observed in other low- and middle-income countries, where occupational hazard exposure remains high due to weak regulatory enforcement and limited workplace safety infrastructure. Studies from sub-Saharan Africa have consistently shown that timber and small-scale industry workers are exposed to multiple hazards in poorly regulated environments.^{31 32} In contrast, lower exposure levels reported in more regulated settings have been attributed to stronger occupational safety systems, effective enforcement, and improved workplace conditions.³⁵ This suggests that differences in institutional capacity and regulatory enforcement play a critical role in determining occupational risk.

The present study also identified inadequate workplace safety infrastructure, including limited availability of first aid facilities, safety information materials, and occupational health services. Such deficiencies increase workers' vulnerability to injuries and long-term health complications. These findings are consistent with previous studies in Nigeria and other African countries, where informal sector workers often lack access to essential occupational health services.^{40,41} The absence of structured occupational health systems in these settings continues to pose a major public health challenge.

Importantly, this study found that education level, employment type, and work experience were significantly associated with occupational hazard exposure. Workers with formal education were less likely to experience high hazard exposure, possibly due to better awareness of occupational risks and safer work practices. Similarly, workers employed in structured workshop settings had lower exposure compared to self-employed workers, likely reflecting better access to safety resources and some level of organizational oversight. Workers with longer work experience also demonstrated lower exposure, which may be attributed to increased familiarity with workplace risks and adaptive safety behaviors over time.

However, these associations should be interpreted with caution. Given the cross-sectional design of the study, causal relationships cannot be established, and the observed associations may be influenced by unmeasured confounding factors or reverse causation. Additionally, the observed relationship between longer work experience and lower hazard exposure may partly reflect a healthy worker survivor effect, where workers who experience severe hazards may leave the occupation earlier.

The findings of this study have important policy and public health implications. Despite the existence of occupational safety policies in Nigeria, enforcement remains weak, particularly in informal sector industries. Strengthening regulatory inspection systems, improving access to workplace safety infrastructure, and integrating occupational health services into primary healthcare systems are critical steps toward reducing occupational hazard exposure. Furthermore, targeted safety education and training programs should be implemented, especially for less educated and self-employed workers who may be more vulnerable to unsafe working conditions.

This study has some limitations. The use of self-reported data may introduce recall and reporting bias, potentially leading to misclassification of hazard exposure. Although an observational checklist was used to complement self-reported data, some degree of measurement bias may persist. In addition, the study was conducted in a single Local Government Area, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other settings. Future studies should consider longitudinal designs and objective exposure measurements to

better establish causal relationships and quantify hazard levels.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated a high prevalence of occupational hazard exposure among timber processing workers in Kano State, Nigeria, particularly to wood dust, excessive noise, and mechanical hazards. The findings also revealed inadequate workplace safety infrastructure, including limited availability of first aid facilities, safety information, and occupational health services.

Educational level, employment type, and work experience were significantly associated with occupational hazard exposure, highlighting the role of both socioeconomic and workplace factors in shaping occupational health outcomes.

Overall, the findings underscore the urgent need to strengthen occupational health and safety systems within informal sector industries in Nigeria to reduce hazard exposure and improve worker protection.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Strengthening Occupational Safety Regulation**
Government regulatory agencies should enhance monitoring and enforcement of occupational safety standards within informal timber processing industries to ensure compliance with hazard control measures and workplace safety guidelines.
2. **Improvement of Workplace Safety Infrastructure**
Workshop owners and industry stakeholders should prioritize the provision of essential safety infrastructure, including functional first aid kits, safety information materials, machine guarding, proper ventilation systems, and dust and noise control measures.
3. **Occupational Health Education and Training**
Regular occupational health education and safety training programs should be implemented to improve workers' awareness of hazards, promote safe work practices, and encourage the use of protective measures.
4. **Expansion of Occupational Health Services**
Periodic occupational health screening, particularly for respiratory and hearing conditions, should be integrated into healthcare services to enable early detection and management of work-related health problems.

5. Targeted Interventions for Vulnerable Workers
Interventions should focus on workers with lower levels of education, self-employed workers, and those with limited work experience, as these groups may be more vulnerable to hazardous working conditions.

6. Multi-sectoral Collaboration

Government agencies, occupational health institutions, and industry associations should collaborate to design and implement sustainable occupational health and safety programs for informal sector workers.

Study Limitations

This study has some limitations. The cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causal relationships between variables. Data were partly based on self-reported responses, which may be subject to recall and reporting bias. Although an observational checklist was used to complement self-reported data, some degree of measurement bias may persist. Additionally, the study was conducted in a single Local Government Area, which may limit the generalizability of the findings.

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